

REGIONAL COOPERATION AND INTEGRATION IN CENTRAL ASIA: AN INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

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Introduction

Central Asia, a vast region comprising Kazakhstan, Kyrgyz Republic, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan occupies a critical geopolitical and economic space in Eurasia. India, with its rising power status, has strategically engaged with the region, focusing on energy security, trade, counter-terrorism and geopolitical influence. As part of its “Connect Central Asia” policy, India has sought to expand its ties and foster regional integration. This article examines India’s approach to regional cooperation and integration in Central Asia, highlighting the opportunities and challenges that shape its foreign policy.

Historical Context of India-Central Asia Relations

India’s historical ties with Central Asia date back to the ancient Silk Road, where the region played a crucial role in trade, culture, and the dissemination of ideas. These historic links have left a lasting cultural imprint on both India and Central Asia, particularly through the spread of Buddhism and intellectual exchanges. However, post-Soviet independence in 1991 shifted India’s engagement with the region, prompting a renewed focus on strategic, economic, and cultural ties.

The dismantling of the Soviet Union provided India with new opportunities but also challenges in fostering closer cooperation with Central Asian republics. Despite the geographical distance, India’s interests in Central Asia have expanded, particularly due to the region’s rich energy resources, strategic location and emerging markets.

Regional Cooperation and Integration in Central Asia

Central Asia’s abundant natural resources and strategic location make it an important player in the adjustment of the international political and economic structure. At the same time, the topic of Central Asian integration has long elicited heated debates among various stakeholders. The regional integration process of the Central Asian countries following their independence can be delineated into three distinct phases.

The initial phase, spanning from 1990 to 2005, was characterized by the emergence of collaborative endeavors among the region’s newly sovereign states. The subsequent phase, spanning from 2005 to 2016, brought a period of stagnation in terms of regional integration within Central Asia. This was primarily due to the integration of the Central Asian Cooperation Organization into the Eurasian Economic Union, which was predominantly influenced by Russia. The current phase, spanning from 2017 to the present, has witnessed a resurgence in efforts at regional integration. Central Asian countries have initiated annual consultative meetings to address and tackle regional issues and challenges, signifying a renewed commitment to fostering collaboration and cooperation among the nations.

In another boost to regional integration, Uzbekistan has made significant progress in demarcating and delimiting its borders with neighboring countries. The resolution of border disputes between Uzbekistan and Tajikistan, as well as Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan, has had a positive impact on regional stability and cooperation. By successfully reaching border

agreements with all its neighbors, Uzbekistan has demonstrated its commitment to regional integration and cooperation.

Regional cooperation and integration in Central Asia primarily focus on promoting economic development and improving living standards through collaborative efforts. This involves building infrastructure, particularly transportation and energy, and facilitating trade and policy cooperation. The region also benefits from increased connectivity and mobility, both for people and goods, contributing to shared prosperity and sustainable economic growth.

Economic cooperation, infrastructure development, trade and policy cooperation, connectivity, addressing shared challenges, intra-regional contacts are important issues which need to be addressed in an effective and adequate manner.

Current instrumentalities in place - Central Asia Regional Economic Cooperation (CAREC), Consultative Summits, Eurasian Economic Union (EEU), Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO).

Geostrategic Considerations and Security Cooperation

Central Asia's proximity to Afghanistan has made it a critical region in the fight against terrorism. India has been keen to collaborate with Central Asian states on counter-terrorism initiatives, particularly through multilateral frameworks such as the Shanghai Cooperation Organisation (SCO), of which India became a full member in 2017. India's membership in the SCO has facilitated cooperation with Russia, China, and Central Asian republics on issues such as drug trafficking, extremism, and regional instability. Additionally, India's security strategy has been strengthened through bilateral military engagements, such as joint exercises with Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, fostering closer defence and counter-terrorism cooperation. These initiatives are vital to India's long-term regional security strategy.

Economic Connectivity and Infrastructure Development

India's efforts to strengthen regional connectivity through initiatives like the International North-South Transport Corridor (INSTC) have the potential to significantly enhance trade between Central Asia, Russia, and India. This corridor, which passes through Iran, aims to reduce transportation costs and transit times, thereby boosting trade across the Eurasian landmass. India's investments in the Chabahar Port in Iran also contribute to regional connectivity, offering an alternative trade route that bypasses Pakistan and connects Central Asia to the Arabian Sea.

Moreover, India's membership in the Ashgabat Agreement (2018), a multi-modal transport agreement with Central Asia, Iran, and Oman, further advances India's regional connectivity goals. The development of transport infrastructure remains a key pillar of India's long-term strategy for Central Asia, positioning the region as a critical trade hub between Asia and Europe.

Diplomatic and Multilateral Engagements

India's diplomatic engagement with Central Asia has deepened through various platforms, including the India-Central Asia Dialogue, initiated in 2019. The dialogue has proven to be an effective mechanism for discussing and advancing issues of mutual concern, including regional security, trade, and cultural cooperation. Through this platform, India has enhanced its ties with the region, engaging with Central Asian leaders on a range of political, economic, and security matters. Additionally, the India-Central Asia Business Council (ICABC), established in 2020, promotes business exchanges and investment opportunities, contributing to the economic integration of Central Asia and India. This has facilitated the flow of Indian technology, expertise, and capital into the region, further strengthening economic ties.

Technological and Space Collaboration

India's growing capabilities in space technology and digital infrastructure have opened new avenues for cooperation with Central Asia. The Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO) has initiated capacity-building partnerships, particularly with Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, in

areas such as remote sensing, satellite navigation, and disaster management. Central Asian states, eager to modernise their digital economies and monitor environmental degradation (like the Aral Sea crisis), see India as a valuable partner in developing indigenous capabilities in space-based applications.

Countering Islamist Extremism through Ideological Engagement

Beyond traditional counterterrorism, India aims to combat the ideological spread of radical Islamism in Central Asia through soft power and strategic religious engagement. Given Central Asia's secular yet Muslim-majority profile, India has emphasised its model of pluralism and co-existence as a counter-narrative to Wahhabi-Salafi influences from the Gulf. Quiet but targeted cultural diplomacy—like the promotion of Indo-Sufi traditions and academic cooperation in Islamic studies—supports India's effort to ideologically insulate the region from transnational extremism. This strategic engagement bolsters internal stability in the CARs and reinforces India's role as a moderate force in the Islamic world.

Access to Rare Earth Minerals and Critical Raw Materials

Central Asia holds untapped reserves of rare earth elements (REEs), including uranium, lithium, and other critical raw materials essential for India's transition to clean energy and advanced manufacturing. With the global supply chain dominated by China, India sees Central Asia as a potential strategic supplier to diversify its sourcing. Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, in particular, have shown openness to cooperating in mineral exploration and processing, aligning with India's Minerals Strategy and Atmanirbhar Bharat (self-reliant India) initiative.

Cultural Continuity and Buddhist Diplomacy

India is increasingly leveraging its Buddhist heritage to build spiritual and cultural bridges with Central Asian republics, especially with Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, which host archaeological remnants of ancient Buddhist influence. India has supported restoration projects, museum collaborations, and digital archiving of Buddhist artifacts. This "Buddhist diplomacy" is a form of cultural realism asserting civilisational depth.

Promoting Regional Stability through Proactive Security Partnerships

The evolving security dynamics in and around Afghanistan create an opportunity for India to assert a stabilising role through intelligence sharing, capacity-building of local law enforcement, and deradicalisation initiatives. India's participation in regional security platforms like the SCO, along with bilateral military exercises and counter-terrorism collaborations, can be deepened to enhance trust and long-term regional resilience.

Advancing Sustainable Development and Climate Collaboration

Central Asia's environmental vulnerabilities—ranging from desertification to water stress—create space for India to emerge as a key sustainability partner. India's leadership in the International Solar Alliance, digital solutions for water management, and expertise in arid agriculture offer a blueprint for green cooperation. Joint projects in renewable energy, smart irrigation, and a forestation can turn ecological vulnerability into a platform for shared innovation and climate diplomacy.

Conclusion

India's engagement with Central Asia reflects a strategic pursuit of energy security, economic growth, and regional stability. As the region becomes increasingly important in global geopolitics, India's efforts to foster regional cooperation and integration will be key to its long-term objectives. India's diplomatic, economic, and cultural outreach provides a robust foundation for future cooperation in Central Asia, offering opportunities for mutual benefit. As India continues to strengthen its ties with the region, it must remain adaptive and proactive in addressing emerging challenges and leveraging its unique strengths. The future of India-Central Asia relations will depend on India's ability to navigate complex geopolitical rivalries, foster greater economic integration, and contribute to regional peace and security.

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